

IEAGHG 7th Post Combustion Capture Conference

25th to 27th September 2023 Pittsburgh, PA, USA

Development needs and knowledge gaps of CESAR1 solvent

D. Morlando^a, A. Hartono^a, V. Buvik^b, H.M. Kvamsdal^b, E.F. da Silva^b, H.F. Svendsen^a,
H. K. Knuutila^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemical Engineering, NTNU, NO-7491 Trondheim, Norway

^bSINTEF Industry, NO-7465 Trondheim, Norway

Abstract

The reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions is a major global challenge in the fight against climate change. Among the various technologies available for post-combustion CO₂ capture, amine-based absorption is currently considered the most advanced and cost-effective [1]. However, the absorption process incurs a significant energy penalty, prompting research efforts to develop new energy-efficient solvents for widespread implementation of CO₂ capture. One such alternative to the commonly used ethanolamine (MEA) is an aqueous blend of 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) and piperazine (PZ). Research has shown that CESAR1 (a blend of 3.0 M AMP and 1.5 M PZ) demonstrates lower energy consumption [2], lower degradation rates [3], [4] and higher loading capacity than MEA [5]. CESAR1 solvent's non-proprietary nature, independence from a specific technology provider, and superior performance compared to MEA make it a compelling choice as an alternative for MEA.

As the technology has not yet undergone full optimization and technology qualification for commercial deployment, it is crucial to assess both the experimental and modelling gaps. A systematic literature review was conducted to identify gaps in the experimental studies within the AURORA project (<https://aurora-heu.eu/>). The work focused on:

- Physical and transport properties: density, viscosity, surface tension and diffusivity
- Equilibrium properties: vapor-liquid equilibrium, solid-liquid equilibrium and freezing point depression, speciation, and equilibrium reaction constant data
- Kinetics properties
- Solvent degradation data including degradation compounds
- Pilot data, including solvent emissions and aerosol formation
- Available property and simulation models

Selected findings are shown in Figure 1 qualitatively. The figure shows, for example, that even though many properties are available, data on absorption kinetics of CO₂ loaded solution is not available and only limited data is available for viscosity of the loaded system even though both of these directly impact the absorption performance.

* Corresponding author. E-mail address: hanna.knuutila@ntnu.no

Property	AMP/H ₂ O	PZ/H ₂ O	AMP/PZ/H ₂ O	AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	AMP/PZ/H ₂ O CO ₂
Density	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow
Viscosity	Green	Green	Yellow	Red	Green	Yellow
Diffusivity	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red	Red
Kinetics	Green	Green	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Red
VLE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow
ΔH_{abs}	White			Green	Green	Green
\mathcal{H}	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Red	Red
Degradation	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow

Figure 1: Qualitative preliminary results of the literature review on selected properties. Legend: -Data unavailable, -Gaps identified, -Data available.

In the presentation, we will shortly summarize:

- The identified gaps in experimental data and the available models
- The available pilot data and amine emission data
- Summarize the knowledge on degradation of CESAR1.

The main emphasis will be on the opportunities and challenges related to the CESAR1 solvent and since the aim of the AURORA project is to qualify the CESAR1 solvent for commercial deployment, the presentation will further include the plan for closing the remaining gaps.

Acknowledgments

This research has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101096521.

Keywords: post-combustions capture; amine-based absorption; solvent characterization; CESAR1 solvent; literature review.

References

- [1] B. Dutcher, M. Fan, and A. G. Russell, "Amine-based CO₂ capture technology development from the beginning of 2013-a review," *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 2137–2148, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1021/am507465f.
- [2] H. P. Mangalapally and H. Hasse, "Pilot plant study of two new solvents for post combustion carbon dioxide capture by reactive absorption and comparison to monoethanolamine," *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 66, no. 22, pp. 5512–5522, Nov. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.ces.2011.06.054.
- [3] J. N. Knudsen, J. Andersen, J. N. Jensen, and O. Biede, "Results from test campaigns at the 1 t/h CO₂ post-combustion capture pilot-plant in Esbjerg under the EU FP7 CESAR project".
- [4] T. Wang and K.-J. Jens, "Oxidative degradation of aqueous PZ solution and AMP/PZ blends for post-combustion carbon dioxide capture," *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, vol. 24, pp. 98–105, May 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2014.03.003.
- [5] W.-J. Choi et al., "Removal of carbon dioxide by absorption into blended amines: kinetics of absorption into aqueous AMP/HMDA, AMP/MDEA, and AMP/piperazine solutions," *Green Chem.*, vol. 9, no. 6, p. 594, 2007, doi: 10.1039/b614101c.